

Artist Report

1. Carloine Shaw

The first time I heard Caroline Shaw's music it was different from anything I had ever heard. I am a fan of all of her works, particularly her series or string quartet pieces on her album "orange", but the first piece of hers I ever heard is still my favorite, *Partita for 8 Voices*. This is the piece that won her the 2013 Pulitzer Prize for Music, that she workshopped, recorded and toured, with the new music vocal group *roomful of teeth*. I remember being shown this piece by a friend and just thinking "I have never heard vocal music like this in my life." What caught me was how expressive Shaw's music was with minimal text. It wasn't my first interaction with vocal music that used extended techniques like vocal fry, throat singing, and using phonetic vowels instead of words. However, Shaw's use of wordless melodies had an inherent and unique musicality that was distinct from how say, Ligeti or Berio would use phonetic vocal techniques. The opening of the first movement *Allemande*, layering spoken text with sung vowels, and how the voices move from independent to unison, still gives me an electric shock. I would put the first movement in a list of pieces that I believe to be perfectly paced, musically. Everything you hear is significant, and everything you hear is moving. Shaw's *partita* managed to use all of this but so viscerally that it felt natural to listen to, like this is what vocal music should be. At the time I was studying music by very successful composers that while I admired conceptually did not particularly compel me musically. It was too far away from the music I had experienced up to that point. Shaw's music had (and still has) this unique expressive ability that never fails to inspire me in return.

2. Jordan Key

I met Jordan while studying for my masters and while he was pursuing his doctorate. Jordan's music has had a striking influence on me, in that in the time I've known him, I've been able to witness the progression of his craft. From piece to piece in the years we overlapped in school, I have seen his concerted effort to improve elements of his craft based on what was successful and what failed to deliver in a given project. What still resonates with me however, isn't how Jordan improved his craft while in school - that is the de facto reason one attends classes in composition. It was that Jordan's music remained unequivocally unique, his own. He was simply improving on his ability to communicate this music to an audience and elevating the artistry with which this is accomplished.

Above all, this strong aesthetic - an element of one's music that most composers spend lifetimes trying to manifest - is a product of Jordan's authentic experience. Jordan is an atheist, a gay man, and in the time I've known him, his sight has degraded to a point at which society would classify him as disabled, and he now requires the assistance of a cane and a seeing eye dog when venturing out into public. In his undergraduate studies he spent a year living in a monastery in provincial France, learning plain chant from monk practitioners and meditating for hours a day. In addition to singing chants, he is an incredibly talented organist, and also plays the bagpipes. His work has been deeply influenced by composers like Conlon Nancarrow, a communist at the height of the Red Scare who lived in exile in Mexico, writing music for player pianos of such complexity that computers have a hard time reproducing it 50 years later. He is also a well versed theorist and poet, and has an impressive grasp of antique and classical philosophy, western literature, and musicology. His free time is spent making score videos for obscure medieval and renaissance chant works on youtube, in addition to planning a new private academy for high school students in Gainesville in hopes of providing them a more

rounded education then what is offered in the public school system (this is a joint venture with his partner - a doctorate in mathematics and otherwise equally accomplished person.)

This unique collection of attributes and experiences permeates every piece of Jordans in a way that I always have found to be bravely honest. He writes works like "Chants for the Church of Naught" - a mass for atheists, or "Threnody on the Death of Children" - a musical response to school shootings, or "To Say Pi" - a black MIDI ballet and love letter to mathematics. These pieces are so uniquely his, such pure culminations of his influences and life experiences that only he could produce. The piece of his that I still return to, to this day is a work for soprano, flute, double bass and fixed media entitled "Meditation on the death of Stephen Hawking" (one of Jordan's Idols.) I saw the piece premiered in 2019. It combines recordings of different leaders and thinkers from around the world, along with some of Hawking's speeches as well, to create a narrative meditating on the role of humanity in the universe. The trio of acoustic musicians interact with the fixed media and play around it as it progresses. For him to have tackled such a large concept - and to have translated it into musical moments that gave most of the audience chills - was nothing short of one of the most impressive musical experiences in my life.